

**The Transformative Role of Artificial Intelligence in Enhancing Nigerian Education,
Including Its Applications, Benefits, and Challenges**

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Abstract

Education goes beyond just memorizing facts and vocabularies; it essentially focuses on problem-solving skills and the ability to work collaboratively in a team environment. The integration of Artificial Intelligence (AI) in education has the potential to revolutionize the learning experience in Nigeria. With the increasing demand for high-quality education, AI can help address the challenges faced by the Nigerian education system, such as inadequate infrastructure, shortage of qualified teachers, and limited access to educational resources. The integration additionally addresses how AI-driven tools can improve educational outcomes by providing instant feedback, improving accessibility and enabling predictive analytics to support student performance. The objective of this study is to provide a comprehensive understanding of the potentiality of AI to influence the future of higher education, with the aim of fostering more effective, inclusive, and adaptive learning environments. This paper focuses on how ideas are understood and employed. It can be concluded that AI can advance educational practices by influencing data-driven curriculum development, intelligent tutoring system, and adaptive learning experience. To this end, it could be recommended that the use of AI and harnessing its potentiality are essential to create a better future for all. Government should among others, invest in training programs for teachers and other education professionals so as to prepare them for the challenges of the 21st century

Keywords: Artificial Intelligence, Educational Resources, Intelligent Assessment, Smart Tutoring System, Educational Robot

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Introduction

Education is very essential to our lives as it helps us all to achieve our greatest potential in life. Artificial Intelligence is ubiquitous in the lives of twenty-first century citizens and is heralded as a technology that can improve and advance every aspect of our lives (Górriz et al., 2020). AI has quickly become a game-changer across industries, with education being the most impacted. Redefining traditional teaching methods that pave way for inclusive education and preparation for the future. According to Jagadeesh (2020), he observed that many colleges and other educational institutions are gradually abandoning the traditional teaching methods over time as they become outdated. In Education, AI is the intelligent machine that helps children learn. Murtaza, Ahmed and Shamsi (2022) described AI as the key advantage in education in which it is the ability to provide personalized learning experiences for students. Smartphones are increasingly powerful tools that people rely on to quickly search and find information. Janelle, (2019) was of the opinion that tablets are gradually replacing textbooks in classrooms due to the increasing use of technology

According to Teach Flow (2023), the main goal of AI in education is to improve the efficiency and quality of teaching through the use of technology. It is used to better identify and support unique needs of each student. AI has the potential to innovate teaching and learning approaches while addressing some of the major issues facing education today. It is able to streamline processes that require human intervention and address important issues such as different learning styles of students. Immersion learning is one of the several educational applications of Artificial Intelligence, it gives students more autonomy over their own learning processes and provides them with real-life experiences that they can apply on a daily basis outside of school hours. According to Tira (2021), technology has also impacted people's lives and changed the way we work, learn, and communicate. As today's students enter the workforce, they enter a labor market that is drastically different to that of previous generations due to advances in Artificial Intelligence (Ning & James, 2023). Andrea (2024) also noted that educating children about AI is crucial to promote digital literacy, sharpen their critical thinking skills, and prepare them for future academic and professional success. Due to the speed at which technology is evolving, it is critical to integrate AI education into the curriculum so as to ensure that all students are well-equipped for their academic future and also for their professional development.

Learning AI also pushes students to examine and evaluate complicated material, question presumptions, and consider the moral implication of using AI. This approach can result to cost savings and open up new avenue for exploring pedagogical ideas that might not be feasible in the traditional classroom. AI promises to transform the education landscape by improving student experiences, supporting teachers, and providing more personalized learning opportunities (Eric and Tiachong, 2023). Despite its promising potential, its application in education is still inconsistent as some students are often left out of the latest technological advancements. As we leverage these emerging powerful technologies, it's important that we teach our students about their advantages and demonstrate how to use these tools appropriately, ethically, and responsibly. Tutors must also have the skills and strategies necessary to use this new technology to teach the material, improve and streamline daily procedure, and improve the learning environment.

The Nigerian education system faces numerous challenges, including inadequate infrastructure, shortage of qualified teachers, poor funding and limited access to quality educational resources (Obeza, 2023). These challenges have resulted in poor academic performance, high dropout rates, and a significant gap in the quality of education between Nigeria and other developed countries. Furthermore, the conventional teaching methods used in Nigerian schools often focus on rote memorization and theoretical knowledge, rather than practical skills and critical thinking, which are essential for success in the 21st-century workforce. Despite the potential of technology to enhance education, the integration of digital tools and innovative teaching methods has been slow in Nigeria. The country's education system has not fully leveraged the potential of Artificial Intelligence (AI) to improve learning outcomes, increase access to education, and enhance the overall quality of education. Therefore, the study aims to provide a clear and concise overview of AI in education, to help people understand its concept, benefits, and challenges.

The Concept of Artificial Intelligence

The term AI is not new as various authors have defined it based on their own experiences and perspectives. It is widely accepted that Artificial Intelligence (AI) is a field within Computer Science that aims to create intelligent machines that can perform tasks that traditionally require human intelligence. In the educational context, AI refers to the use of these intelligent machines and algorithms to improve various aspects of the learning process. According to Popenici and Kerr (2017), AI refers to computer systems that can perform human-like functions including learning, adapting, synthesizing, self-correction, and using data for complicated processing tasks. Keng (2018) also defined AI as an information technology-based computer system or machine capable of completing tasks that normally require human intelligence and logical reasoning. AI is a tool used in many academic fields, such as Medical education (Winkler-Schwartz et al., 2019), Engineering education (Shukla et al., 2019), Mathematics education (Hwang & Tu, 2021), and Language education (Liang et al., 2021).

The concept of AI in education encompasses a variety of technologies and applications, including natural language processing, data analytics, machine learning and robotics. These tools enable both teachers and students to have personalized learning experiences, adaptive assessment, intelligent tutoring systems, and more. Current applications of AI in higher education range from automated assessment systems to adaptive learning environments that tailor educational content to the needs of each individual students. McCarthy invented the term in 1956, following on from Turing's work and building on Turing's (1937, 1950) that were earlier research, Cristianini, (2016). Over time, developments in machine learning, natural language processing, and data analytics have expanded the capabilities of AI and enabled its integration into a wider range of educational tools and platforms. Turing (1937) initially proposed the existence of intelligent thought and reasoning that could be used to create intelligent machines.

Artificial Intelligence in Education

Education is the fundamental right for all Nigerian children and the government has made efforts to expand access to education across the country. A primary purpose of education is to teach young people how to acquire knowledge, create awareness and be of good behaviours in the society in other to live in peace with each other. Today, AI has the potential to address some of the biggest challenges in education, innovate teaching and learning practices and accelerate progress toward Sustainable Development Goal, (Fawas, 2023). By incorporating AI into Nigerian education system, education can become more interesting, accessible, and relevant for students of all ages and backgrounds. It will allow them to practice and develop their skills in a safe and regulated environment. According to Janelle (2019), integrating and leveraging technology in the classroom will help students prepare for the obstacles and challenges of the digital in the future. He further explained that it ensures the students have the necessary skills to progress through college and their future career. AI should be viewed as a solution to a global problem because it integrates a variety of technologies to transform the way students learn and how we prepare the next generations for the future. AI not only increases students' enjoyment and engagement with learning, but also motivates them to put more effort in their studies over time (Janelle 2019).

The Applications of AI in the Field of Education

As AI continue to develop rapidly so its application in the education sector is of great important. The specific use of AI in education is not just about reducing the teacher's workload, but also about helping children learn faster, feel more confident, and achieve their goals. Ema (2024), pointed out that AI in education is not about replacing teachers, but rather that AI tutors and chat bots can support teachers and provide individual support for student learning. These virtual assistants make the learning experience more efficient and focused and make the school more fun. Here are some examples of AI applications in education:

Intelligent Assessment and Grading: AI is one of the latest developments in education that has changed the way tests are designed and administered contrast to the past, when it came to the assessment of students' result or overall performance was determined using assessment cards or student performance reports. AI has the potential to transform student assessment practices and be used to improve assessment outcome in education. Valentine et al. (2023) discussed Turnitin's AI program, which uses Natural Language Processing (NLP) to evaluate writings and provide feedback on grammar, spelling, and syntax. It is also used to detect plagiarism and assist teachers in assigning grades more quickly and accurately. Compared to the old assessment approach, intelligent assessment is a significant improvement as it is more accurate, efficient, and faster. It also relieves teachers of the burden of correcting homework, and can significantly streamline the correction process (Mary and Mohamed, 2023). By using automated grading systems, teachers can focus more on essential tasks such as lesson planning and supporting students, resulting insignificant time savings (Adiguzel et al, 2023). When a teacher processes a lot of student data, errors can occur that can affect grades or provide inaccurate information about a student's ability. However, automated AI assessment can minimize errors and use data in a new impactful ways.

Teachers can also evaluate students more fairly by using AI to grade long-form responses like essays. All of this contributes to the increased productivity of educators instead of going through and assigning grades by hand.

Smart Tutoring System: Mary and Mohamed (2023) described the intelligent tutoring system as one of the adaptive learning systems that can achieve better teaching results. This system can provide student with personalized support and feedback helping them improve their writing skills and produce higher quality written work. (Adiguzel et al, 2023). With the use of smart learning system, an intelligent tutoring system accelerate students' acquisition of knowledge points and helps them achieve specific learning goals. Through the feedback mechanism, the teacher can have a better understanding of whether students have mastered the classroom content, and use emotional perception to predict and adjust it. (Mary and Mohamed, 2023)

Educational Simulation Game: A key component of modern education concepts is high-quality teaching. Consequently, the teaching environment does not have to be lifeless, but rather presented in a more entertaining manner. Educational simulation games built on a simulation environment promote transparency in education and teaching, which can increase students' excitement for learning. Active learning with simulations and game enables students to actively experiment, test and apply what they have learned in different and complex situations. It also enables students to learn something new and then encourage reflection about their experiences (Alina, 2012). Through intelligent simulation games, students can develop new perspectives, become more engaged in the learning process, and effectively exercise their observational and critical thinking skills that will encourage them to take initiative in problem-solving and learning new information (Mary and Mohamed, 2023).

Educational Robot: As technology advances, educational robotics have become an increasingly popular tool for teachers and students in education sector. The use of educational robots in the teaching-learning process for students will raise the educational standards of the next generation of leaders giving them a competitive advantage over their peers and keeping pace with the best educational practices in the world. Robotics is not only aimed at students who are passionate about coding and programming, but also helps them develop their abilities and gain thorough a comprehensive understanding of robotics via proactive collaboration and communication with their peers. In specific teaching applications, educational Robots are an intelligent teaching tool that can be a powerful supplement for teachers to carry out teaching activities. Students can also actively search for answers to questions through this human-computer interaction and develop their capacity for self-learning (Mary and Mohamed, 2023). Robotics in education is designed to support the next generation of students in their knowledge acquisition. These robots can act as peer mentors, small group leaders, teaching assistants, or personal tutors, interacting with students through facial characteristics similar to humans and emotion-perceiving technologies. (Matthew, 2024).

The Benefits of AI in Educational System

Artificial Intelligence is taking the world by storm and many people are skeptical about its potential risks, but there are also many benefits that can be reaped from it as well. The area of education has witnessed significant progress in the field of AI. The use of this technology into classrooms holds great potential for improving student learning. It has several positive impacts on education, helping teachers, students, and schools administration. Additionally, AI makes top-notch materials accessible to everyone by facilitating universal access to education. It can tailor education to each student's requirements and speed as well as allowing for more personalized learning experiences. Alexandara (2023) described AI in education as a tool that can lead to better students' outcome and that can make students learn at their own pace and in a way that suit their learning style. By evaluating student performance data, AI-powered solution can determine which students require assistance to enhance their learning experience. Artificial Intelligence is not meant to replace teachers; rather, it is about improving and enhancing student learning. It saves teachers time by automating administrative activities, enabling them to concentrate more on lesson planning and interacting with students. AI in education is crucial for fostering digital literacy, critical thinking skills and preparing students for future academic and career success (Hector and Michelle, 2023). With the help of AI, teachers may stay up to date on pedagogical techniques which helps them advance professionally and stay current with best practices in education.

The Challenges of AI in Educational System

AI is a potentially powerful tool for learning and people are wondering if this time will be different from previous times when technological advancement has consistently created more new jobs than it has destroyed. One reason for this assumption is that the main issue posed by AI is job losses, which will lead to social unrest. A concern among educators is that the development of AI technology could automate teaching task and making their roles obsolete by replacing human tutors and teachers in the future. Milad and Ghazal (2024) pointed out that, if AI is widely used in education, some teaching tasks could be automated and this could result in the displacement of teachers from their positions. The replacement of human teachers with AI could lead to social isolation and less personal interaction. It may also make students to be less engaged in their studies. McKinsey Global Institutes Report estimates that by 2030, automation may displace between 400 and 800 million individuals that is up to one-fifth of the global work force (Yosef, 2023). These individuals will need to switch job categories and learn new skills. According to George (2017) research, there was a 5.6 reduction in employment for every robot added to the United State of America (USA) economy. It is observed that within the next three decades, Artificial Intelligence will surpass human understanding. Jack Ma, as quoted by (Marguerite, 2017), employers will be seeking for students with experience in data analytics as this is a talent that calls for analytical thinking, diverse approaches to data interpretation, and autonomous thought. Additionally, as AI becomes more widely used in education, some teaching functions may be automated, which could result in the displacement of teachers and support staffs from their positions (Milad and Ghazal, 2024).

Integrating AI technology into educational environments can be expensive and require thorough staff and teachers' training. To incorporate AI technologies into educational system, schools may need to make costly investments in new hardware, software, and infrastructure to support AI tools, which can be a significant financial burden. Moreover, teachers and staff may need to spend significant time on learning how to effectively use AI tools and make them lose time that could be spent on teaching and supporting students. Teachers and staff may also need to devote a significant amount of time to learning on how to utilize AI technologies efficiently

Conclusion

In conclusion, integrating AI into education has the potential to completely transform the educational process by making it more relevant, accessible, and engaging for students of all ages and backgrounds. AI has the potential to help Nigeria students, teachers and educational institutions in many ways by increasing the benefits of personal learning, assessment, and efficiency. To fully utilize AI in education, we must provide fair access to AI resources and change our curricula to incorporate AI related ideas. The students' creativity and entrepreneurship will be encouraged and will also be equipped for the labour market in the future. This conclusion supports Julia Horowitz (2017) submission that in the next 30 years the best CEO for the Time Magazine will likely be a robot because a robot remembers than a person, it count faster and it won't be angry with competitors. He further stated that robot is better in processing large amount of data which poses too great challenge for our human capabilities. As AI continues to evolve, it is important to address ethical issues, ensure equity, and prioritize teacher support and training. By integrating AI, education can become more engaging, accessible, and relevant for students of all ages and backgrounds, allowing them to practice and develop their skills in a secured and controlled environment.

Recommendations

To fully harness the benefits of AI in Nigerian education and to overcome the associated challenges, the following recommendations are proposed:

- i. The Nigerian government, through the ministry of education should formulate clear policies and guidelines to integrate AI into all levels of education, with particular emphasis on AI curriculum development.
- ii. Government should invest in training programs for teachers and other education professionals to improve their skills in AI technology, address concerns about job displacement and prepare them for the challenges of the 21st century.
- iii. Educational institutions should invest in AI infrastructure and resources to improve student learning outcomes.
- iv. The long-term impact of AI on education should be evaluated by researchers through longitudinal studies.
- v. Educational leaders should encourage collaboration between educators, developers, and researchers to drive AI innovation in education.

- vi. Parents and guardians should be educated about AI powered tools and their potential impact on student learning.

References

- Adiguzel, T., Kaya, M.H., and Cansu, F.K. (2023). “*Revolutionizing education with AI: Exploring the transformative potential of ChatGPT*”. Contemporary Educational Technology, 15(3), ep 429.
- Alexandara Harry (2023). “*Role of AI in Education*” Interdisciplinary Journal and Humanity (INJURITY) 2(3):260-268.
- Alina Zapalska (2012). “*Development of Active Learning with Simulations and Games*” US China Education Review, ISSN 15486613, D David publishing.
- Andrea W. (2024) “*From virtual tutors to accessible textbooks: 5 ways AI is transforming education*” world economic forum. May 10.
- Cristianini, N. (2016). “*Intelligence reinvented*” New Scientist, 232(3097), 37–41.
- Ed Lauder (2027). “*Jack Ma says in 30 years we will feel the ‘pain’ of AI*” <https://aibusiness.com> April 24.
- Ema Lukan (2024). “*Uses of AI in Education*” <https://www.sythensia.io> September 16,
- Eric Chic Keung Cheng and Tianchong Wang (2023). “*Leading digital Transformation and Eliminating barriers for teachers to incorporate artificial intelligence in basic education in Hong Kong*” Computers and Education: Artificial Intelligence. Vol (5).
- Fawas Olamide Ibrahim (2023). “*The impacts of emerging AI technologies on Nigeria education*” www.susanafrica.com April 5.
- George Dvorsky (2017) “*Robot are already replacing human workers at an alarming rate*” Tech news, Gizmodo USA. March 28.
- Górriz, J. M., Ramírez, J., Ortíz, A., Martínez-Murcia, F. J., Segovia, F., Suckling, J., Leming, M., Zhang, Y. D., Álvarez-Sánchez, J. R., Bologna, G., Bonomini, P., Casado, F. E., Charte, D., Charte, F., Contreras, R., Cuesta-Infante, A., Duro, R. J., Fernández-Caballero, A., Fernández-Jover, E., ... Ferrández, J. M. (2020). “*Artificial intelligence within the interplay between natural and artificial computation: Advances in data science, trends and applications*”. Neurocomputing, 410, 237–270.
- Hector Bojorquez and Michelle Martinez Vega (2023). “*The Importance of Artificial Intelligence in Education for all Students*” IDRA Newsletter ISSN 109-572, Vol (1) no (5).
- Hwang, G. J., & Tu, Y. F. (2021). “*Roles and research trends of artificial intelligence in mathematics education: A bibliometric mapping analysis and systematic review*” Mathematics, 9(6), 584.
- Jagadeesh Kengam (2020) “*Artificial Intelligence in Education*” Science and Technology Department, Bournemouth University, Bournemouth, United Kingdom.
- Janelle Cox (2019), “*Benefits of Technology in the Classroom*” K-12 Teachers Alliance. Teachhub.com. November 7.

- Julia Horowitz (2017). “*Jack Ma: We Need to Stop Training our kids for Manufacturing Jobs*” CNN Business news, September 20.
- Keng L. Siau (20218). “*Education in the Age of Artificial Intelligence: How Will Technology Shape Learning?*” Singapore Management University 7(3):22-24.
- Liang, J. C., Hwang, G. J., Chen, M. R. A., & Darmawansah, D. (2021). “*Roles and research foci of artificial intelligence in language education: An integrated bibliographic analysis and systematic review approach*” Interactive Learning Environments.
- Marguerite Ward (2017). “*Jack Ma: This is what to study if you want a high-paying job in the future*” <https://www.cnbc.com>. June 23
- Mary Louis and Mohamed ElAzab (2023). “*The Future of Teaching and Learning in Artificial Intelligence era*” International Journal of Internet Education
- Matthew Urwin (2024). “*7 Examples of Robotics in Education to Know Robots are improving the education industry in various ways, and these seven companies are accelerating this trend*” <https://built-in.com>. Jul 08.
- Milad Shahvaroughi Farahani1, Ghazal Ghasmi (2024). “*Artificial Intelligence in education: A comprehensive study*” Forum for Education Studies, 2(3), 1379.
- Murtaza M, Ahmed Y, Shamsi JA, (2022). “*AI-Based Personalized E-Learning Systems: Issues, Challenges, and Solutions*” IEEE Access. 2022; 10: 81323-81342.
- Ning Wang & James Lester (2023), “*K-12 Education in the Age of AI: A Call to Action for K-12 AI Literacy*” International Journal of Artificial Intelligence in Education. Vol. 33, pp 228–232. June 20.
- Obeza E Luise (2023), “*The Quality of Educational Development in Nigeria*” International Research Journals. Vol 14, issues 2
- Popenici, S. A. D., & Kerr, S. (2017). “*Exploring the impact of artificial intelligence on teaching and learning in higher education*” Research and Practice in Technology Enhanced Learning, 12(22), 1–13.
- Teach flow (2023). “*The Evolution of AI in Education: Past, Present, and Future*” Teachflow.AI <https://teachflow.ai/the-evolution-of-ai-in-education-past-present-and-future/> . April 22
- Tira, N. F. (2021), “*Artificial Intelligence (AI) In Education: Using AI Tools for Teaching and Learning Process*” Institut Teknologi Bisnis AAS Indonesia. ISSN Online: 2654-6590 | ISSN Cetak: 2654-5306. Senin, December 20
- Turing, A. M. (1937). “*On computable numbers, with an application to the Entscheidungs problem*” Proceedings of the London Mathematical Society, 2(1), 230–265.
- Turing, A. M. (1950). Computing machinery and intelligence. Mind, 59, 443–460.
- Valentine Joseph Owan, Kingsley Abang, Delight Omoji Dika and Bassey Asuquo Bassey (2023). “*Exploring the potential of artificial intelligence tools in educational measurement and assessment*” Article in Eurasia Journal of Mathematics, Science and Technology Education.

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Winkler-Schwartz, A., Bissonnette, V., Mirchi, N., Ponnudurai, N., Yilmaz, R., Ledwos, N., Siyar, S., Azarnoush, H., Karlik, B., & Del Maestro, R. F. (2019). “*Artificial intelligence in medical education: Best practices using machine learning to assess surgical expertise in virtual reality simulation*” *Journal of Surgical Education*, 76(6), 1681–1690.

Yosef Nesirat (2023). “*800 Million Jobs could be lost to AI and automation by 2030*”. <http://Leadershipbydesign.com> April 2nd